

Suppl. Table 11

HIGH section

Module	ASV ID	Domain	Phylum	Class
	3235	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
M5	187	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
	3104	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	3065	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	15	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
	76	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
	315	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
	2982	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	2981	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	2979	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	3134	Bacteria	Sva0485	NA
	70	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
	2971	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
M4	121	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
	94	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
		Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata Marine Benthic Group D and
	3090	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	3069	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
	109	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
	146	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
	3063	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria

3060	Bacteria	Chloroflexi	Anaerolineae
2982	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
122	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
3067	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
29	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3073	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
56	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3090	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3238	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Thermodesulfovibrionia
88	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
125	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
103	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
78	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
26	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3102	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3227	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3004	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3162	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Acidimicrobiia
58	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
2976	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
85	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
261	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3025	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Coriobacteriia
136	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria

M1

82	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2995	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
30	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
144	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3264	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
67	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
77	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
38	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3168	Bacteria	Spirochaetota	Spirochaetia
42	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
294	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3199	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
276	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
27	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

M10

63	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3064	Bacteria	Sva0485	NA
100	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2983	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
3171	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfobacteria
3076	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
4	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
52	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

157	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2997	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia
23	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
113	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata

Taxa

M2

2988	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3099	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Thermodesulfovibrionia
3009	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Incertae Sedis
197	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
2974	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
125	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
3091	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
176	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
137	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3164	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
40	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
74	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
106	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3078	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfobacteria
8	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
14	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
9	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3013	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
2977	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2990	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae

M3

3077	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria
65	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
1	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2970	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3213	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfobacteria
6	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
304	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
215	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
84	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
2975	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia
110	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
28	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
198	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3127	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
40	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
236	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
59	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
31	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
87	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2964	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
60	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3129	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria

LOW section

M13

2987	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3028	Bacteria	Campilobacterot	Campylobacteria
3068	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
73	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata

M6

226	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3071	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
20	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
43	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
69	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
57	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
231	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
4	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
212	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3004	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3090	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3092	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobio	Lentisphaeria

M22

79	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3209	Bacteria	MBNT15	NA

M1	3094	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gamma	Proteobacteria
	21	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea
	3020	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfu	Monadia
	3114	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria	
	2969	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria	
	3287	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gamma	Proteobacteria
	135	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea
	3014	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Thermodesulf	Vibrionia
	18	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia	
	3037	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfu	Monadia
	3033	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia	
	26	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia	
	66	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea
	22	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea
	34	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata	
131	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea	
12	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria		
M5	156	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria	
	2991	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia	
	3200	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gamma	Proteobacteria
	3115	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Syntrophia	
	3122	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Thermoleophilia	
	2	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathy	Archaea

2979	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
142	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
35	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
201	Archaea	Micrarchaeota	Micrarchaeia
174	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
8	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
56	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata

M7

2988	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3059	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria
108	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
76	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
3237	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
108	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
232	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
97	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
14	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
134	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3105	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
49	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata

M16

10	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
223	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria

3176 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
3138 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Acidimicrobiia
3056 Bacteria Proteobacteria Alphaproteobacteria

M2

3315 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia
3125 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Actinobacteria
3124 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia
3 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
2971 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
3022 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
281 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
3025 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Coriobacteriia
3163 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia
109 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
3284 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
45 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria
3189 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
3144 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia
2963 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
25 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria
3057 Bacteria Desulfobacterota Desulfobacteria

M3

6 Archaea Halobacterota Methanosarcinia

129	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3006	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Syntrophorhabdia
63	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3190	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3273	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
68	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3111	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia
3058	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia
5	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
37	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
1	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2994	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
60	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
81	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
13	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3079	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Thermodesulfovibrionia

MEDIUM section

M8

2989	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
12	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
18	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
59	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

75 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata

50 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia

98 Archaea Halobacterota Methanosarcinia

M6

3026 Bacteria Desulfobacterota Syntrophia

149 Archaea Crenarchaeota Nitrososphaeria

14 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia

3117 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia

3012 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

3146 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Acidimicrobia

3055 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

2981 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

3007 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

2990 Bacteria Verrucomicrobio Verrucomicrobiae

44 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata

61 Archaea Crenarchaeota Nitrososphaeria

2986 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

M3

76 Archaea Crenarchaeota Nitrososphaeria

196 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria

2977 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

3074 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria

32 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia

3042	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
204	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2992	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli
2994	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3207	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
86	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2962	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
16	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
3004	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
132	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2976	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
67	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
120	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
68	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3034	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2985	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
24	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
43	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
52	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
21	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3083	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
M7	3153	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobiae
	3104	Bacteria	Proteobacteria
	40	Archaea	Thermoplasmata

3154	Bacteria	Sva0485	NA	
2983	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia	
63	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia	
2967	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	
6	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia	
139	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria	
5	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata	
3010	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	
34	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata	
110	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata	
2987	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	
131	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia	
3071	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	
2996	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia	
170	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria	
77	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata	
90	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria	
3167	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia	
2997	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia	
3065	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	
130	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia	
M9	3051	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
	41	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata

10	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3246	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
17	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
82	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2972	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Ignavibacteria
2995	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
3095	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
3036	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
35	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2979	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2966	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2969	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria
3049	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3019	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria
19	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

M1

222	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
3059	Bacteria	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria
70	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3052	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3196	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Desulfuromonadia
3006	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Syntrophorhabdia
3092	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobia	Lentisphaeria
36	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

119	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3040	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
162	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
300	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
188	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
8	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2964	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2984	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
3169	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
3121	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3041	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3039	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobio	Verrucomicrobiae
74	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
2964	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2984	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
2968	Bacteria	Desulfobacterotæ	Desulfobacteria
56	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
3045	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
191	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
151	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
3098	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobio	Verrucomicrobiae
3070	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3126	Bacteria	Desulfobacterotæ	Desulfuromonadia
3183	Bacteria	Sva0485	NA
224	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

97 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
23 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
126 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia

M2

81 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
2970 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
3077 Bacteria Proteobacteria Alphaproteobacteria
3017 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
247 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
101 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria
3008 Bacteria Gemmatimonadetes Gemmatimonadetes
7 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
62 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
192 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
2982 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
27 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
200 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
74 Archaea Crenarchaeota Nitrososphaeria
28 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
3118 Bacteria Desulfobacterota Desulfobulbia
3031 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
69 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
3038 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Actinobacteria
106 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia

3027	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
3139	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobio	Verrucomicrobiae
136	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
313	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
216	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
208	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3066	Bacteria	Desulfobacterot	Desulfobacteria
157	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3194	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
54	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
M10			
51	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3068	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3023	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
107	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
2975	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia
3119	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria
123	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
208	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3067	Bacteria	Desulfobacterot	Desulfuromonadia
85	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
2991	Bacteria	Myxococcota	Myxococcia
88	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia
3106	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia
79	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia

84 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata
3009 Bacteria Firmicutes Incertae Sedis

M11

39 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
92 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
175 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria
33 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata
3033 Bacteria Myxococcota Myxococcia
3 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
3011 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
150 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata
100 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
38 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata
150 Archaea Thermoplasmato Thermoplasmata
46 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
45 Archaea Euryarchaeota Methanobacteria
3193 Bacteria Bacteroidota Bacteroidia
26 Archaea Halobacterota Methanosarcinia

M5

2980 Bacteria Actinobacteriota Thermoleophilia
3080 Bacteria Bacteroidota Bacteroidia
2974 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
246 Archaea Crenarchaeota Bathyarchaeia
2974 Bacteria Proteobacteria Gammaproteobacteria
122 Archaea Crenarchaeota Nitrososphaeria

35	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
71	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
53	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
164	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
2965	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
30	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3101	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
158	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
140	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
25	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3063	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
137	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
29	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3223	Bacteria	Verrucomicrobia	Verrucomicrobiae
60	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3001	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
128	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
65	Archaea	Halobacterota	Methanosarcinia

M4

3142	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria
108	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3109	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
138	Archaea	Thermoplasmata	Thermoplasmata
3089	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Ignavibacteria
3022	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria

20	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
48	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
37	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
78	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
124	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
11	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
3052	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3044	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Nitrospira
3053	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia
57	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
91	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
121	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3222	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
31	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
29	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3000	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2993	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
2988	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
15	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia

M6

83	Archaea	Euryarchaeota	Methanobacteria
3015	Bacteria	Desulfobacterota	Syntrophia
2963	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3021	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria

221	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
13	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
2971	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
80	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
153	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
22	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
31	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
96	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
2	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3072	Bacteria	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia
99	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3032	Bacteria	Nitrospirota	Thermodesulfovibrionia
42	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
72	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Nitrososphaeria
3024	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
73	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata
1	Archaea	Crenarchaeota	Bathyarchaeia
3035	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria
3030	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria
105	Archaea	Thermoplasmato	Thermoplasmata

Order	Family	Genus	Species
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	NA	NA
Run-SP154	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	
Arenicellales	Arenicellaceae	NA	NA
Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA

SJA-15	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Arenicellales	Arenicellaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Burkholderiales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	NA
Burkholderiales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
Microtrichales	Ilumatobacteraceae	Ilumatobacter	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
OPB41	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Geothermobacteraceae	Geothermobacter	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Cellvibrionales	Spongiibacteraceae	BD1-7 clade	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
Spirochaetales	Spirochaetaceae	Spirochaeta	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Bacteroidetes VC2.1 Bac22	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae	NA	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	NA	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Methylobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
DTU014	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	Desulfatirhabdium	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Geothermobacteraceae	Geothermobacter	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	NA	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA

Rhizobiales	Hyphomicrobiaceae	Hyphomicrobium	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	Sva0081 sediment g	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Sulfurisoma	NA

Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
Campylobacterales	Sulfurimonadaceae	Sulfuricurvum	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobrevibacteri	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
SCGC AB-179-E04	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
Arenicellales	Arenicellaceae	NA	NA
Oligosphaerales	Lenti-02	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanoperedenaceae	Candidatus Methan	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Burkholderiales	Methylophilaceae	Methylotenera	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	Geobacter	NA
Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Pseudarthrobacter	NA
PeM15	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Rhizobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	Geobacter	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Chromatiales	Chromatiaceae	NA	NA
Syntrophales	Syntrophaceae	Syntrophus	NA
Gaiellales	Gaiellaceae	Gaiella	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Micrarchaeales	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Methylobacter	NA
Micrococcales	Intrasporangiaceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Nitrosomonadaceae	Ellin6067	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	NA	NA

Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
Microtrichales	Ilumatobacteraceae	CL500-29 marine gr	NA
Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Tabrizicola	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Frankiales	Sporichthyaceae	Longivirga	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Rhizobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
OPB41	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Rhodoferax	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Burkholderiales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	NA	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	Desulfatirhabdium	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Syntrophorhabdales	Syntrophorhabdaceae	Syntrophorhabdus	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Ferribacterium	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Peptostreptococcales-Tissier	Peptostreptococcaceae	Romboutsia	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanoperedenaceae	Candidatus Methan	NA
Syntrophales	Smithellaceae	Smithella	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Microtrichales	Ilumatobacteraceae	Ilumatobacter	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
Run-SP154	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanosphaera	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	Geobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Bacillales	Bacillaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	Candidatus Nitrocos	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
Cellvibrionales	Haliaceae	Halioglobus	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Cellvibrionales	Spongiibacteraceae	BD1-7 clade	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA	NA	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Ignavibacteriales	PHOS-HE36	NA	NA
Geothermobacteraceae	Geothermobacter	NA	NA
Chitinophagales	Chitinophagaceae	Dinghuibacter	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
PeM15	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
PeM15	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Micrococcales	Intrasporangiaceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
Geothermobacteraceae	Geothermobacter	NA	NA
Syntrophorhabdales	Syntrophorhabdaceae	Syntrophorhabdus	NA
Oligosphaerales	Lenti-02	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanoperedenaceae	Candidatus Methan	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	Candidatus Nitrocos	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Actibacter	NA
Chitinophagales	Saprospiraceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Methylophilaceae	Methylotenera	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Actibacter	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	Sva0081 sediment g	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Hydrogenophilaceae	Thiobacillus	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Rhizobiales	Hyphomicrobiaceae	Hyphomicrobium	NA
Burkholderiales	SC-I-84	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacterales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Gemmatimonadales	Gemmatimonadaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Desulfobulbales	Desulfocapsaceae	[Desulfobacterium]	NA
Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Arenimonas	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Micrococcales	Intrasporangiaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA

Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobrevibacteri	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Desulfobacterales	Desulfosarcinaceae	Sva0081 sediment g	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Rhizobiales	Methyloligellaceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Geobacterales	Geobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Clostridiales	Clostridiaceae	Clostridium sensu st	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanoperedenaceae	Candidatus Methan	NA

Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
DTU014	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
Myxococcales	Anaeromyxobacteraceae	Anaeromyxobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Rhodoferax	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Gaiellales	NA	NA	NA
Sphingobacteriales	Lentimicrobiaceae	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
SG8-5	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Nitrosomonadaceae	Ellin6067	NA
Methanobacterales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacterales	Methanobacteriaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Pedosphaerales	Pedosphaeraceae	ADurb.Bin063-1	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Nitrosomonadaceae	Ellin6067	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
Methanosarciniales	Methanosaetaceae	Methanosaeta	NA
Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Rhodobacter	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Ignavibacterales	Ignavibacteriaceae	Ignavibacterium	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Rhizobacter	NA

Marine Benthic Group D and NA		NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanomassiliicoccales	Methanomassiliicoccaceae	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Comamonadaceae	Leptothrix	NA
Nitrospirales	Nitrospiraceae	Nitrospira	lenta
Clostridiales	Clostridiaceae	Clostridium sensu st	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	Candidatus Nitrocos	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Burkholderiales	Sutterellaceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Methylobacter	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Methanobacteriales	Methanobacteriaceae	Methanobacterium	NA
Syntrophales	NA	NA	NA
Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Dechloromonas	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA

NA	NA	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
Methylococcales	Methylomonadaceae	Crenothrix	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Bacteroidales	Bacteroidetes vadinHA17	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Nitrososphaerales	Nitrososphaeraceae	Candidatus Nitrocos	NA
Steroidobacterales	Steroidobacteraceae	NA	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA
NA	NA	NA	NA
Cellvibrionales	Haliaceae	OM60(NOR5) clade	NA
Rhizobiales	Xanthobacteraceae	Bradyrhizobium	NA
Marine Benthic Group D and	NA	NA	NA